

The efficacy of the Praat Program for self-improvement in English pronunciation of Chinese EFL university students

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ABSTRACT

The current study investigates the efficacy of the *Praat* Program (hereafter *Praat*) in improving Chinese English as a foreign language (EFL) in university students' English pronunciation. Pronunciation is one of the essential components of speaking skills as it helps enunciate the intended meaning. However, it is also one of the most challenging aspects due to a lack of practice or opportunity to use English regularly or receive corrective feedback or objective evaluation from an independent source. 18 Chinese EFL university students participated in the study, and training sessions were held on *Praat*. The study lasted six weeks. The participants took two English pronunciation pretests from PTE "Read Aloud" tests before participating in the training sessions. They received ongoing technical support during their *Praat* use. At the end of Week 6 of their participation, they were given two English pronunciation posttests. Statistical comparisons between the pretest and posttest results suggested significant pronunciation improvement ($p < 0.05$) with a moderate effect size. Six participants were then recruited for individual interviews based on their pronunciation performance to investigate their perceptions of *Praat* and factors that explained their processes and efficacy in using *Praat*. Qualitative results suggest that the students perceived *Praat* as helpful in improving their pronunciation (e.g., providing listening input, opportunities for output, and feedback on their pitch contour, which was not ordinarily available to them in the English learning context). Factors such as *Praat*'s stress-free environment were identified as influential in helping them use *Praat* effectively.

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INTRODUCTION

Pronunciation is a sub-skill of speaking, which is critical to communicative success in an English as the lingua franca world (Björkman, 2013). For this reason, pronunciation is considered elementary for learning a foreign language and improving speaking skills (Mahdi & Al Khateeb, 2019). However, despite the increased importance of communicative competence (Canale & Swain, 1980), many studies have reported that pronunciation is often overlooked in the curricula of English in English as a foreign language (EFL) country (e.g., Alghazo, 2015; Baker & Murphy, 2011; Sakale, 2012), in which English is not a medium of everyday communication (Neri et al., 2006).

Over the past few decades, computer-assisted pronunciation training (CAPT) applications have captured great attention in linguistics and language education. They have been used to improve English learners' pronunciation (Mahdi & Al Khateeb, 2019), which is considered as one of the most challenging skills in English learning and teaching (Haghighi & Rahimy, 2017; Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2017; Sadeghi & Mashhadi Heidar, 2016). Most CAPT applications are designed to allow users to view their pronunciation and compare it with model pronunciation (Li et al., 2016). To achieve this aim, CAPT applications are usually equipped with Automated Speech Recognition (ASR), which visualises users' speech signals and presents users' prosodic features, such as their pitch (Tsai., 2015). Such functions can be used to diagnose and assess their users' English pronunciation, provide feedback, and assist the users in improving their English pronunciation (Agarwal & Chakraborty, 2019). For example, *Praat*, developed by Paul Boersma and David Weenink of the University of Amsterdam, is an application which allows its users to record their pronunciation and view it in the form of pitch contours. These features of *Praat* have been argued to enable its users to compare their English pronunciation to native speakers' vocally and visually (Osatananda & Thinchana, 2021).

The present study investigates *Praat*'s effectiveness and usefulness in helping Chinese university (EFL) students improve their English pronunciation. Little is known about how it can be integrated into a classroom context to assist Chinese EFL students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, CAPT has captured the attention and interest of many researchers due to the widespread availability of CAPT programs on the market and the widespread use of CAPT programs by universities and language institutes (Pourhosein et al., 2019). For example, Neri et al. (2008) conducted a study to explore the effectiveness of the *Parling* Program on 28 Italian EFL children's English segmental pronunciation. The experimental group used *Parling* to train the pronunciation of the target words by listening to and reading an English story. In contrast, the control group was taught using a traditional "reading after the English teacher" way. The results revealed that the experimental and control groups made comparable and significant progress in their English segmental pronunciation. Both groups significantly improved difficult English words in their study, possibly unknown to the participants before the study. However, Luo's (2016) study revealed that CAPT applications contributed to 55 Taiwanese English-major first-year students' more significant progress in their English segmental pronunciation than in-class instructions. Furthermore, a few empirical studies have investigated the effects of CAPT applications on EFL learners' suprasegmental pronunciation features (e.g., Felps et al., 2009; Hardison, 2004; Tanner & Landon, 2009; Tsai, 2015). For example, 75 EFL learners who participated in Tanner and Landon's (2009) 13-week study were divided into one experimental group using a CAPT application called Cued Pronunciation Readings (CPRs) and one control group. The pretest and posttest results revealed that CPRs significantly influenced the experimental group's suprasegmental pronunciation features, including pausing, word stress and intonation.

Input provided by CAPT

Listening is an essential category of input that lays the foundations of speaking for EFL learners since listening allows learners to improve their pronunciation, vocabulary, and phrases (Listiyarningsih, 2017). Although it is not realistic for EFL teachers to provide adequate FL listening materials in traditional classrooms, EFL learners are given adequate opportunities to receive authentic input on CAPT applications (Mahdi & Al Khateen, 2019; Rogerson-Revell, 2021; Thomson, 2011). Rogerson-Revell (2021) added that various audio input sources could be available on CAPT applications, such as educational websites and social media. These categories of audio input enable FL learners to hear and see how FL pronunciation is expressed.

Output provided by CAPT

EFL learners should have sufficient opportunities to practise their target language and to produce comprehensible output. Sidgi and Shaari (2017) stated that EFL output on CAPT applications promotes EFL learners' speech production due to a stress-free environment, where EFL learners are more willing to use the pronunciation learning materials and to produce their speech. Those audio-learning materials provide EFL learners with diverse kinds of pronunciation practice, such as repeating EFL phonemes, answering questions structurally and interacting authentically in contexts (Rogerson-Revell, 2021). These pronunciation practices benefit EFL learners' confidence in their oral language (Sidgi & Shaari, 2017).

Feedback provided by CAPT

One crucial reason CAPT applications are helpful to EFL learning is the feedback they provide for EFL learners (Mahdi & Al Khateeb, 2019). CAPT applications can provide users with two main kinds of useful feedback. The first category is corrective feedback. Feedback is imperative for EFL pronunciation improvement (Sato & Lyster, 2012), which Li (2010) referred to as the response to a learner's non-target-like L2 production. This type of response has been justified by Schmidt's (1990) Noticing Hypothesis, which claims that corrective feedback can boost FL learners' linguistic awareness. Neri et al. (2008) found that corrective feedback can improve FL learners' segmental pronunciation features. The use of ASR holds the key to segmental feedback (Neri et al., 2002). Although ASR may not teach FL learners how to produce a single phoneme or a word, it can inform FL learners when their pronunciation is non-target-like. This advantage contributed to the popularity of using ASR in CAPT applications (Hansen, 2006). Visual feedback is another important kind of feedback on CAPT applications (Mahdi & Al Khateeb, 2019). According to Thomson (2011), visual feedback allows EFL learners to compare their EFL pronunciation properties with native speakers' pronunciation features. This is based on Tsai's study (2015), which stated that visual feedback enables FL learners to contrast their pitch contours with a model teacher's pitch contours, meaning that FL learners can better understand the differences between their pronunciation and model pronunciation. Such an advantage of visual feedback seems to be the most effective way of improving suprasegmental pronunciation features (Neri et al., 2002). Presenting suprasegmental pronunciation features in pitch contours and visual feedback of

CAPT applications makes suprasegmental pronunciation features more understandable to FL learners (Thomson, 2011).

Research Questions

The above studies and theories show that CAPT applications benefit EFL learners' English segmental and suprasegmental pronunciation. However, personality, as one of the most recognised individual differences (Irani et al., 2003), has been considered an essential factor influencing people's ways of learning (Lawrence, 1997). Irani et al. (2003) added that different personalities can lead to different views about the same teaching method. Few studies have investigated people's perceptions of CAPT applications that differ in their personalities. Thus, in addition to the effectiveness of *Praat*, this study investigates the research participants' perceptions towards their pronunciation learning through *Praat*. Two research questions were addressed in this study:

1. To what extent does *Praat* improve Chinese EFL university students' pronunciation quality?
2. How do students perceive the usefulness and limitations of *Praat*?

RESEARCH METHOD

Research participants

The participants were 18 Chinese-speaking EFL university students (eight males and ten females) aged between 18 and 24 (mean = 21.4, SD = 1.539). All of them had read and signed two documents related to ethical considerations: *Participant Information Statement and Participant Consent Form*. They had all been learning English for approximately 15 years since primary school. In addition, it was ensured that the research participants had received minimal professional training experience in English pronunciation before.

Prior to the commencement of this study, the participants were invited to take an English language proficiency test (<https://www.transparent.com/learn-english/proficiency-test.html>). The results indicated that all 18 final participants' English proficiency levels were intermediate. During the study, all participants were requested not to participate in other English pronunciation training.

The current study also investigated the perceptions of Chinese EFL university students of the usefulness of *Praat*. Six research participants were invited to individual semi-structured interviews based on their performance in the posttests (high, average, and low). The definition of each performance level is based on a concordance report between PTE Academic and IELTS Academic published by Clesham and Hughes (2020) (see Appendix A). Gender balance was also considered, so three males and three females participated in the individual semi-structured interviews. The details of these participants are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. List of interview participants

Student Name (Pseudonym)	Age	Gender	Pronunciation test performance	Average overall scores of two posttests
Jenny (P1)	21	F	High	83.750
Harvey (P4)	19	M	High	78.050
Jeffrey (P6)	21	M	Average	54.100
Faye (P9)	20	F	Average	56.200
Leo (P11)	19	M	Low	29.450
Maggie (P15)	20	F	Low	33.900

Research instruments

The instruments used in this study included a technological pronunciation learning application (*Praat*), pronunciation learning materials (an English native speaker's pre-recordings), four English pronunciation tests (two pretests and two posttests), and six individual semi-structured interviews.

Praat

Praat is a linguistic software package created by Paul Boersma and David Weenink from the University of Amsterdam (Styler, 2013). It allows its users to record their voices and see their pitch contours (Boersma & van Heuven, 2014). The pitch

contour diagrams visualise users' intonation and word stress (Boersma & van Heuven, 2014). For example, rising pitch contours represent rising intonation, while falling pitch contours represent falling intonation.

Figures 1 and 2 below present Martin's (Participant 2, average achiever) and an English native speaker's pitch contour feedback diagrams of the same sentence (The goal of anthropology is to provide a holistic account of humans and human nature.) in Training Session 1. It can be observed that there were more changes in the native speaker's intonation when he read the sentence, while Martin's (Participant 2) intonation was more monotonous. It was expected that the research participants would improve their English intonation by comparing *Praat's* pitch contour diagrams after the training sessions.

Figure 1. Martin's pitch contours provided by Praat

Figure 2. The native speaker's pitch contours provided by *Praat*

The Pronunciation tests

In this study, the participants received four English pronunciation tests, including two pretests (one week apart) and two posttests (one week apart). Appendix B presents Pretest 1 as an example. In each pronunciation test, the participants were asked to read ten short English texts from the “Read Aloud” tests of the Pearson Test of English Academic (PTE Academic). In PTE “Read Aloud” tests, test candidates are given 30-40 seconds to look at an English text and another 40 seconds to read the short text (Pearson, n.d.). The test candidates can start reading the text once the preparation time is over. In this study, every question was recorded only once.

PTE Academic was chosen for this study for two reasons. Firstly, PTE features accurate automated marking without human interference (Pearson, 2022). Secondly, the “read aloud” test merely assesses the participants’ pronunciation in terms of their “content”, “pronunciation”, and “oral fluency”. By contrast, IELTS speaking tests require test candidates to generate ideas (Fernandez, 2018); TOFEL speaking tests measure test candidates’ ability to communicate in English, so reading and listening are also included in speaking tests (Bridgeman et al., 2012). Appendix C presents a detailed description of each criterion.

Training materials

On *Praat*, the maximum length of audio is set at 10 seconds. Thus, in each of the two English training sessions, the researcher prepared 20 shorter sentences. The texts were extracted from the “read aloud” tests of the Duolingo English Test (DET). It is a computer-adaptive test of English proficiency accepted by many universities for admission purposes (Wagner & Kunnan, 2015). Appendix D presents the texts used in Training Session 1 as examples. Subsequently, the participants recorded their pronunciation repeatedly and tried to imitate the native speaker’s pronunciation by looking at his pitch contours and listening to his recordings repeatedly.

Semi-structured interviews

In this study, semi-structured interviews were used to collect the qualitative data. During the interviews, the 21 interview questions (see Appendix E) developed based on RQ2 guided the interviewees to share their perceptions of *Praat*’s advantages and disadvantages. All the interviews were conducted in Chinese.

Research procedure

This study employed a sequential Quan → Qual MMR design (Ivankova & Greer, 2015). It began with two English pronunciation pretests (one week apart). Then, the participants took part in two one-hour *Praat* training sessions, where each participant was assigned to a personal breakout room so that they would have private space for practice without being disturbed by each other.

During the training sessions, the participants were informed of the basic concepts of English segmental and suprasegmental pronunciation features, such as stress and rising and falling intonation. They were given 20 English sentences to read and a native speaker’s pre-recordings to imitate. The researcher visited each participant’s breakout room, listening to them read the short English texts. The researcher provided the participants with slight hints when they asked for help. However, the instruction time was limited to five minutes because it was expected that the results of their posttests would not be influenced by the instruction time.

After the training sessions, the participants received two English pronunciation posttests. Finally, six participants were invited to participate in an individual semi-structured interview. Figure 3 below presents the entire research procedure.

Figure 3. The procedure of this study

Data analysis

Both quantitative and qualitative data analyses were used to address the research questions. The participants’ quantitative data were all entered into and analysed on IBM SPSS Statistics 26. Descriptive statistics were calculated, including mean scores, standard deviations and medians. Cronbach’s alpha (1951) reliability analysis was conducted on IBM SPSS Statistics 26. The results revealed that each of the four pronunciation tests had a reliability of 0.90 or above. Paired-samples *t*-tests and effect size were computed to determine whether the participants improved their English pronunciation significantly ($p < 0.05$) after two *Praat* training sessions.

Finally, the six individual semi-structured interviews were analysed based on Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage thematic analysis, which can be used to identify, analyse, and report the themes of the interviews (Abedin et al., 2021).

RESULTS

This section presents the results of data analysis to answer the two research questions.

Answers relevant to research question 1: To what extent does *Praat* improve Chinese EFL university students' pronunciation quality?

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the participants' pronunciation performance in each pretest and posttest.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of all four pronunciation tests (N = 18)

Criteria	Tests	Mean	Median	SD
Content	Pretest 1	57.711	54.700	16.123
	Pretest 2	57.878	52.900	15.791
	Posttest 1	65.211	66.850	14.696
	Posttest 2	65.022	67.350	14.424
Pronunciation	Pretest 1	44.756	41.700	14.894
	Pretest 2	45.017	41.250	14.652
	Posttest 1	51.272	51.650	14.121
	Posttest 2	51.344	53.600	14.551
Oral fluency	Pretest 1	54.911	52.050	16.057
	Pretest 2	54.483	53.250	15.190
	Posttest 1	59.739	59.800	15.130
	Posttest 2	61.006	60.300	15.310
Overall	Pretest 1	51.183	47.700	15.495
	Pretest 2	51.250	46.700	14.830
	Posttest 1	57.344	57.650	14.309
	Posttest 2	57.711	58.900	14.475

Note. SD = standard deviation.

Table 2 suggests rising trends in the research participants' mean scores of their pronunciation performance across the four categories of scores. As shown in Table

2, their “content” mean scores improved slightly more than the other three kinds of scores. In addition, “pronunciation” seemed to be the most challenging criterion for Chinese EFL university students. The details of each criterion are presented in Appendix C.

To answer RQ1, Noah’s (Participant 5, average achiever) detailed scores in each pronunciation test (Table 3) and his pitch contours (Figures 4 and 5) in one pretest and one posttest are used to illustrate the improvement. Noah was selected because his scores in each pronunciation test were similar to the average scores of 18 research participants. His improvements in English pronunciation might represent the research participants’ improvements in their English pronunciation after *Praat* training sessions.

Table 3. Noah’s (Participant 5) pronunciation test scores

	Pretest 1	Pretest 2	Posttest 1	Posttest 2
Content	52.100	50.500	67.100	66.100
Pronunciation	41.000	42.800	54.700	53.500
Oral fluency	50.300	48.300	57.900	59.200
Overall score	46.700	46.400	58.100	58.100

Figures 4 and 5 below illustrate two short extracts of Question 2 (spend on average eighteen hundred hours per year in our jobs and will work forty years before retirement) in Pretest 1 and Question 8 (along with customary classes on subjects, such as finance and marketing, today’s MBA students) in Posttest 2. It can be observed that Noah had more changes in his English intonation in the posttests, such as the combination of rising tones and falling tones, after two *Praat* training sessions. By contrast, his intonation was monotonous in pretests, with falling tones throughout the text. Based on the official PTE “Read Aloud” criteria, such intonation diversity might have led to his progress in his “pronunciation” scores in PTE “Read Aloud” tests.

Figure 4. Noah’s pitch contours in Pretest 1

Note. The recording was extracted from Question 2 in Pretest 1 due to the ten-second limit.

Figure 5. Noah’s pitch contours in Posttest 2

Note. The recording was extracted from Question 8 in Posttest 2 due to the ten-second limit.

Table 4 presents the results of the paired-samples *t*-tests and Cohen's *d*-value. It shows no statistical differences in the research participants' pronunciation performance between two pretests or posttests ($p > 0.05$). This indicates the participants' pronunciation performance stability in the pretests and posttests. In addition, after two *Praat* training sessions, the eighteen research participants made statistically significant progress ($p < 0.05$) in their overall English pronunciation in the posttests across all four categories of scores. Finally, Cohen's *d*-value results reveal that the two *Praat* training sessions had either medium ($0.5 < d < 0.8$) or large effects ($d > 0.8$) on the research participants' four categories of English pronunciation scores. Therefore, based on the results of descriptive statistics, paired-samples *t*-tests, and Cohen's *d*-value presented above, the answer to RQ1 may be that the *Praat* may significantly improve Chinese EFL university students' English pronunciation performance in medium or large effect size.

Table 4. Paired-samples *t*-test and effect size results (N = 18)

Criteria	Tests	Md	<i>t</i> -statistic	Sig (2-tailed)	Cohen's <i>d</i>
Content	Pre1-Pre2	-0.167	-0.169	0.868	-0.040
	Post1-Post2	0.189	0.276	0.786	0.065
	Pre1-Post1	-7.500	-3.880	0.001	-0.915
	Pre1-Post2	-7.311	-4.305	0.000	-1.015
	Pre2-Post1	-7.333	-3.418	0.003	-0.806
	Pre2-Post2	-7.144	-3.374	0.004	-0.795
Pronunciation	Pre1-Pre2	-0.261	-0.305	0.764	-0.072
	Post1-Post2	-0.072	-0.113	0.911	-0.027
	Pre1-Post1	-6.517	-3.794	0.001	-0.894
	Pre1-Post2	-6.589	-4.173	0.001	-0.984
	Pre2-Post1	-6.256	-3.254	0.005	-0.767
	Pre2-Post2	-6.327	-3.299	0.004	-0.778

Table 4. Paired-samples t-test and effect size results (N = 18)

Criteria	Tests	Md	<i>t</i> -statistic	Sig (2-tailed)	Cohen's <i>d</i>
Oral fluency	Pre1-Pre2	0.428	0.428	0.674	0.101
	Post1-Post2	-1.267	-1.872	0.078	-0.441
	Pre1-Post1	-4.828	-2.801	0.012	-0.660
	Pre1-Post2	-6.094	-3.682	0.002	-0.868
	Pre2-Post1	-5.256	-2.684	0.016	-0.633
	Pre2-Post2	-6.523	-3.360	0.004	-0.792
Overall	Pre1-Pre2	-0.067	-0.077	0.939	-0.018
	Post1-Post2	-0.367	-0.590	0.563	-0.130
	Pre1-Post1	-6.161	-3.643	0.002	-0.859
	Pre1-Post2	-6.528	-4.170	0.001	-0.983
	Pre2-Post1	-6.094	-3.196	0.005	-0.753
	Pre2-Post2	-6.461	-3.397	0.003	-0.801

Note. Md = mean difference.

Answers relevant to research question 2: How do students perceive the usefulness and limitations of *Praat*?

This section presents the themes related to the six selected interviewees' perceptions of *Praat's* usefulness and limitations. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage thematic analysis, presented in Figure 6 below, determined these themes.

Figure 6 Themes on students' perceived usefulness and limitations of *Praat*

When discussing the usefulness of *Praat*, pitch contours were mentioned by the six interviewees most, regardless of their pronunciation performance. The interviewees emphasised that *Praat's* pitch contours made it convenient for them to compare their intonation with the native speaker's so that they could realise the gaps and imitate the native speaker. Leo (Participant 11, low achiever) stated, "I always used falling tones in all the words in English sentences, but I have been able to produce rising tones when reading English sentences after two *Praat* training sessions."

Similarly, all six interviewees considered the availability of unlimited listening input on *Praat* helpful to both English segmental and suprasegmental pronunciation. The two achievers (Jeffrey, Participant 6 and Faye, Participant 9) agreed that repeatedly listening to the native speakers' pre-recordings benefited their segmental and suprasegmental English pronunciation. Similarly, Harvey (Participant 4, high achiever) stated, "I think *Praat* presented the native speaker's recordings pronunciation in a visible way, which was beneficial to my English word pronunciation and intonation."

In addition to the functions equipped with *Praat*, five interviewees agreed that *Praat* can be an essential English pronunciation teaching tool in China. For example, Maggie (Participant 15, low achiever) stated that *Praat* provides child students with “access to idiomatic English pronunciation at a young age, which may positively influence their accent”. Similarly, Faye (Participant 9, average achiever) stated that *Praat* could improve Chinese English-major students’ passion for English pronunciation learning. Furthermore, Jenny (Participant 1, high achiever) stated that the *Praat* could be widely used as an English pronunciation teaching tool in China, where even English teachers may not be experts at English pronunciation due to first language interference.

Personality is widely regarded as an indicator of learners’ differences, which leads learners to have different perceptions of the same educational method (Irani et al., 2003). An interesting finding of the interviews is that four of the six interviewees mentioned introverts might benefit more from *Praat*. Leo (Participant 11, low achiever) and Jeffrey (Participant 6, average achiever) both mentioned that introverts may feel shy and nervous when talking to others face to face. However, they may feel less shy when practising their English pronunciation towards computer screens. In addition, Maggie (Participant 15, low achiever) and Jenny (Participant 1, high achiever) stated that *Praat* provides introverted users with a “stress-free environment where introverted learners can practise pronunciation repeatedly without being heard by others”.

On the other hand, two low achievers (Leo, Participant 11 & Maggie, Participant 15) stated that extroverts are likely to feel bored when they speak to computer screens since extrovert learners may prefer to talk with other people, because they may feel more comfortable if they can see other people’s faces and reactions.

DISCUSSION

This section discusses the main findings related to *Praat*’s effectiveness in improving Chinese EFL university students’ English pronunciation and their perceptions of its usefulness and limitations.

The Effectiveness of *Praat*

The pronunciation test results indicated that *Praat* could help Chinese EFL university students improve their pronunciation of English segments and suprasegments significantly ($p < 0.05$). Such findings are in accord with previous

studies investigating the effectiveness of CAPT applications in improving EFL learner's segmental pronunciation (e.g., Liu & Hung, 2016; Luo, 2016; Neri et al., 2008; Tejedor-García et al., 2020) and suprasegmental pronunciation (e.g., Felps et al., 2009; Hardison, 2004; Tanner & Landon, 2009; Tsai, 2015).

Based on the studies and theories discussed above, Chinese EFL university students' pronunciation improvement might be attributed to *Praat's* listening input, output opportunities, and pitch contour feedback. According to Krashen's (1985) Input Hypothesis, input is indispensable to FL learning success. Celce-Murcia et al. (1996) stated that by listening to model pronunciation, EFL learners can improve their English pronunciation by imitating the model pronunciation. In this study, the participants were provided with a native speaker's model pronunciation to imitate in the training sessions, which might have improved their pronunciation.

According to Swain's (1985) Comprehensible Output Hypothesis, FL learners' comprehensible output could be produced by sufficient FL practice. In this study, the participants had unlimited opportunities to practise their English pronunciation on *Praat*. This might have been an essential reason for the significant improvement in their English pronunciation since sufficient opportunities for output may contribute to FL pronunciation accuracy and fluency (de Bot, 1996; Kendrick, 1997). Furthermore, *Praat* can be used to teach suprasegmental pronunciation with the help of its pitch contour feedback (Le & Brook, 2011). Schmidt's (1990) Noticing Hypothesis suggested that FL learners may have more vital linguistic awareness when they receive visual feedback for their pronunciation. In this study, the participants' improved pronunciation might have resulted from their increased linguistic awareness caused by *Praat's* pitch contours.

Chinese EFL university students' perceptions of *Praat*

The participants perceived *Praat's* pitch contours, unlimited audio input, and valuable output opportunities. Their positive reflections on *Praat* in the interviews might indicate Chinese EFL students' positive emotions when they use *Praat* to improve their English pronunciation. According to Pekrun (2014), negative emotions have damaging impacts on learners' motivation, thereby undermining their learning success (Pekrun, 2014), whereas positive emotions can contribute to more robust learning motivation (Villavicencio & Bernardo, 2013). Gardner and Lambert (1972) stated that FL learners' motivation is closely related to their FL

learning outcomes. Thus, this study may indicate Praat's usefulness in boosting Chinese EFL university students' English learning motivation.

Another finding related to RQ2 is that the participants consider Praat a critical tool for teaching English pronunciation in China. During the six individual interviews, the interviewees mentioned that *Praat* can be an essential tool in China. This is possible because technological tools are necessary to build cost-effective and efficient learner-centred classrooms, where teachers can provide personalised teaching instructions, and students can have individualised study goals (McCombs & Vakili, 2005). Reigeluth et al. (2015) added that learner-centred classrooms provide students with immersive learning environments which boost their motivation.

On the other hand, extrovert Chinese EFL university learners may not enjoy speaking English on computer screens, perhaps because they prefer to practise their English pronunciation by talking to people. Suliman's (2014) study supports this, claiming that extroverts tend to socialise and cooperate in groups when they learn English. Thus, the interviewees stated that Chinese EFL university learners who are extroverts may find using the computer-based *Praat* tedious, dull, or not interactive.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

Some limitations of this study should be noted. The first limitation is that this study does not have a control group or random assignments, so statistical claims on cause-effect are deemed limited (i.e., *Praat* had a significant, positive effect on the research participants' pronunciation test results). To increase the reliability of the statistical findings, a control group (which does not receive *Praat* instruction and use) and randomisation will be needed in future research. Accordingly, the current findings remain suggestive and inconclusive.

The second limitation is that the research participants received only two *Praat* training sessions. In contrast, Tsai's (2015) study provided ten-week training sessions for the research participants to practise their English pronunciation, which might have yielded more robust research results. Therefore, future research needs to increase the treatment period so that observations of learning or non-learning can be better evaluated.

Thirdly, due to the COVID-19 pandemic at the time of data collection, data were collected via an online platform instead of in class or face-to-face, so it can be challenging to claim the generalisability of the instruction and results in a face-to-face classroom. Future research may investigate whether in-classroom CAPT users can improve more significantly than those outside the classrooms.

CONCLUSION

The current study has examined Praat's effectiveness and usefulness in improving Chinese EFL university students' English pronunciation and has discovered their generally positive perceptions of *Praat*. The current findings encourage the use of *Praat* in English pronunciation learning and teaching. Because computer technology will further advance and any limitations or technical issues with *Praat* will likely be resolved, *Praat* will become more user-friendly, and teachers and students will find it much easier to use. Nonetheless, we must remind ourselves that no technology can completely replace teachers, as students need strategic guidance to make their learning effective and pleasurable. Technology is one but not all things that aid teaching and learning.

AUTHOR

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APPENDIX A. 2020 PTE ACADEMIC AND IELTS ACADEMIC CONCORDANCE REPORT

Clesham and Hughes (2020) collected 562 test takers' pairs of PTE Academic and IELTS Academic overall scores. These test takers, who were from 59 distinct countries, spoke 53 different languages. Figure A below presents the concordance results of PTE Academic and IELTS Academic.

Figure A Concordance results of PTE Academic and IELTS Academic

PTE	IELTS	PTE	IELTS
23	4.5	66	7.0
29	5.0	76	7.5
36	5.5	84	8.0
46	6.0	89	8.5
56	6.5		

APPENDIX B. PRONUNCIATION TEST PRETEST 1

1. For graduates looking to give something back, volunteering, either in the UK or overseas, is a popular option. Voluntary projects can cost anything from nothing up to a few thousand pounds, and with that in mind it is essential to look into the project carefully before signing on the dotted line.
2. Most of us spend on average 18 hundred hours per year in our jobs and will work for about 40 years before retirement. When you consider the amount of time spent in the office, you soon realize how important it is to feel a sense of achievement at the end of the day, rather than just meeting financial objectives.
3. Nature offers no greater splendor than the starry sky on a clear, dark night. Silent and jeweled with the constellations of ancient myth and legend, the night sky has inspired wonder throughout the ages—a wonder that leads our imaginations far from the confines of Earth and the pace of the present day and out into the distant reaches of space and cosmic time itself.
4. Yet this landscape, which appeared so alien and confronting to the white settlers and explorers, had been home for thousands of years to Indigenous

Australians for whom the plains, ranges and deserts were a sustaining, spiritual and integral part of their existence.

5. Whether you're climbing your way up the corporate ladder or overwhelmed with the organizational tasks of home and kids, a luxurious vacation to an exotic paradise may seem like an impossible dream. You can only fantasize about an outdoor massage among fragrant island flowers or a nap after enjoying a brunch ripe with fruits fresh from the vine.
6. With a population of only just over 30million living in the world's second largest country, Canada is justly renowned for vast tracts of wilderness untroubled by pollution either from industry or from intensive farming methods. A major conservation issue is the battle to stop the logging of virgin forest in northern Ontario and on the west coast.
7. Smart phones have become an everyday essential for millions of us—we rely on them for everything from updating our social media profiles to banking. Taking out a smart phone contract that bundles together your calls, data, and texts with the cost of the handset can help spread the cost—but can also mean you'll pay more over the long run.
8. During the Early Modern period, the universities of Europe would see a tremendous amount of growth, productivity, and innovative research. At the end of the Middle Ages, about 400 years after the first European university was founded, there were twenty-nine universities spread throughout Europe.
9. The main production of soft drink was stored in 1830's. Since then, from those experimental beginning, there was an evolution until in 1781 when the world's first cola-flavoured beverage was introduced. These drinks were called soft drinks, only to separate them from hard alcoholic drinks. Today, soft drink is more favourite refreshment drink than tea, coffee, juice, etc.
10. Human beings most certainly contribute to climate change by adding greenhouse gases to the atmosphere, but this is only part of the equation. Earth's climate can change over time not only because of changes in the atmosphere but also because of interactions between the atmosphere and various geologic, chemical, biological, and geographic factors.

Appendix C. Detailed Descriptions of Each Criterion of PTE “Read Aloud” Tests

Pronunciation	Descriptions
5 Native-like	All vowels and consonants are produced in a manner that is easily understood by regular speakers of the language. The speaker uses assimilation and deletions appropriate to continuous speech. Stress is placed correctly in all words and sentence-level stress is fully appropriate.
4 Advanced	Vowels and consonants are pronounced clearly and unambiguously. A few minor consonant, vowel or stress distortions do not affect intelligibility. All words are easily understandable. A few consonants or consonant sequences may be distorted. Stress is placed correctly on all common words, and sentence level stress is reasonable.
3 Good	Most vowels and consonants are pronounced correctly. Some consistent errors might make a few words unclear. A few consonants in certain contexts may be regularly distorted, omitted or mispronounced. Stress-dependent vowel reduction may occur on a few words.
2 Intermediate	Some consonants and vowels are consistently mispronounced in a non- native like manner. At least 2/3 of speech is intelligible, but listeners might need to adjust to the accent. Some consonants are regularly omitted, and consonant sequences may be simplified. Stress may be placed incorrectly on some words or be unclear.
1 Limited	Many consonants and vowels are mispronounced, resulting in a strong intrusive foreign accent. Listeners may have difficulty understanding about 1/3 of the words. Many consonants may be distorted or omitted. Consonant sequences may be non-English. Stress is placed in a non-English manner; unstressed words may be reduced or omitted, and a few syllables added or missed.
0 Non-English	Pronunciation seems completely characteristic of another language. Many consonants and vowels are mispronounced, mis-ordered or omitted. Listeners may find more than 1/2 of the speech unintelligible. Stressed and unstressed syllables are realized in a non-English manner. Several words may have the

	wrong number of syllables.
Oral Fluency	Descriptions
5 Native-like	Speech shows smooth rhythm and phrasing. There are no hesitations, repetitions, false starts or non-native phonological simplifications.
4 Advanced	Speech has an acceptable rhythm with appropriate phrasing and word emphasis. There is no more than one hesitation, one repetition or a false start. There are no significant non-native phonological simplifications.
3 Good	Speech is at an acceptable speed but may be uneven. There may be more than one hesitation, but most words are spoken in continuous phrases. There are few repetitions or false starts. There are no long pauses and speech does not sound staccato.
2 Intermediate	Speech may be uneven or staccato. Speech (if ≥ 6 words) has at least one smooth three-word run, and no more than two or three hesitations, repetitions or false starts. There may be one long pause, but not two or more.
1 Intrusive	Speech has irregular phrasing or sentence rhythm. Poor phrasing, staccato or syllabic timing, and/or multiple hesitations, repetitions, and/or false starts make spoken performance notably uneven or discontinuous. Long utterances may have one or two long pauses and inappropriate sentence-level word emphasis.
0 Disfluent	Speech is slow and labored with little discernable phrase grouping, multiple hesitations, pauses, false starts, and/or major phonological simplifications. Most words are isolated, and there may be more than one long pause.

APPENDIX D. TRAINING SESSION 1

1. The goal of anthropology is to provide a holistic account of humans and human nature.

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2. Medium-size motors of highly standardized dimensions and characteristics provide convenient mechanical power for industrial uses.
 3. The spillway entrances are located behind each dam abutment, running roughly.
 4. parallel to the canyon walls.
 5. Much of the backstory to the game is simply alluded to or told through the environment.
 6. The mercenaries spied a military aircraft conducting aerial reconnaissance over the area.
 7. This destruction alters the functioning of the ecosystem and can permanently alter species composition and biodiversity.
 8. The woman was also raped by several pro-Russian rebels from the battalion.
 9. An oligarchy is a government ruled by a small group of powerful people.
 10. Tools are not viewed as involving complex systems which alienate the user from the act.
 11. Widely differing definitions of drug abuse are used in public health, medical and criminal justice contexts.
 12. Centuries of careful selection and breeding have had enormous effects on the characteristics of crop plants.
 13. Chaotic systems are unpredictable in practice due to their extreme sensitivity to initial conditions.
 14. After the war, Soviet politicians again began to control and criticize artistic life very hard.
 15. Some important things they traded were cacao, salt, seashells, jade and obsidian.
 16. At the same time, dharma operates in practical ways beyond mere meaning.

17. He claimed that his decision was because he was concerned for the orchestra's well-being.
18. Rather, it lent its stimulus to linguistic studies, political thought, and scientific research.
19. Following the war, Japanese conservatives briefly returned to politics but were largely purged from public office.
20. The activity of applied mathematics is thus intimately connected with research in pure mathematics.
21. Sociologists have studied the changing structure of these groups.

APPENDIX E. INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. I will ask you questions about your perceptions and opinions about using *Praat* to improve your English pronunciation.

Background information

1. Can you tell me your name, your age and which grade you are in at university?
2. How long have you been learning English?
3. Why are you studying at this educational institution?
4. Is English pronunciation a difficult part for you? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
5. Does your English pronunciation affect your scores on your English tests, such as IELTS and TOEFL? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
6. Has your English pronunciation affected your communication with native English speakers? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
7. Do you think computer-based programs can help you to improve your English pronunciation? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?

Interview questions for RQ2

Now that we have finished the training sessions and posttests, I would like to ask you about your opinions about *Praat*'s effectiveness and limitations.

1. Do you think the visualised pitch contours on *Praat* are helpful to your English pronunciation? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
2. Can you elaborate on how *Praat* and its pitch contours improved your English pronunciation?
3. What are the essential differences between *Praat* and other English pronunciation programs you have used before?
4. Can you elaborate on the advantages of *Praat* in improving English pronunciation?
5. What are *Praat*'s disadvantages in improving English pronunciation?
6. Can *Praat* be an important pronunciation-teaching tool in English classrooms? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
7. Will you recommend *Praat* to your friends to improve their English pronunciation? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
8. Does your language proficiency influence the effectiveness and usefulness of *Praat* on your English pronunciation? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
9. Does your personality influence the effectiveness and usefulness of *Praat* on your English pronunciation? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
10. Do you think the success of *Praat* is affected by your language proficiency and personality? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
11. Do you think *Praat* can be suitable for every single Chinese EFL student? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?
12. Will the learning environment be an essential factor influencing the learning outcomes of pronunciation training via *Praat*? Why or why not? Can you elaborate?